

Conference Abstract

Integrating ecological research for ecosystem understanding across multiple scales: building digital twins of LTER sites

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Abstract

The impacts on ecosystems of global and local shifts in the environment due to e.g. climate change, land use change, and urbanisation present us with complex and interacting societal challenges. Solving a single problem often aggravates another. Scientific insights needed to face these challenges are based on interdisciplinary multi-scale research. It requires that we work together across (sub)disciplinary boundaries and combine our insights and knowledge to understand the complexities and interrelatedness within ecosystems. Making this combination is currently hampered by the availability and scatteredness of datasets and the lack of methods and tools to combine knowledge, data and models. Developing digital twins of ecosystems could provide a paradigm to achieve this combination of knowledge, data and models, and generate the insight and knowledge that we require to face the challenges of global and local change.

A digital twin of an ecosystem is a digital representation of an ecosystem tailored to the user's research objectives and perspective of that ecosystem. They bring together (long-term) data collected of multiple ecosystem facets and across multiple scales, process-based models, and data science and computational modelling tools, making them a versatile instrument. Digital twins can be used to understand ecosystem functioning, by

aiding the discovery of intricate ecological relationships not yet understood or measured. Furthermore, they are ideal for exploring the effects of in situ management strategies, or for the detection of early-warning signals of global change impacts on ecosystem dynamics.

[LTER-LIFE](#) is a scientific infrastructure, embedded in [LTER-NL](#) (Long-Term Ecosystem Research Netherlands) and [LifeWatch ERIC](#), aimed at supporting shared and integrated ecological research, providing scientists the platform and tools to build digital twins of ecosystems. We do this by supporting the sharing of data and models and bringing these together into a site-focused virtual lab where people can work together. LTER sites provide an ideal opportunity for this as they often come with a long history of extensive data collection and research across multiple spheres.

Drawing on experience of building digital twins in the Veluwe LTSE platform, this keynote will take you through the journey of digital twinning parts of an ecosystem with a long legacy of ecological and environmental research and data collection. As these data exist in many different formats, we built data mobilisation and FAIRification pipelines to augment the focal experimental sites in the Veluwe with relevant historical, privately-owned or national datasets. Subsequently, we explored the potential of the Notebook as a Virtual Research Environment ([NaaVRE](#)), which provided us with a virtual lab in which we developed workflows for processing and linking FAIRified data with process-based and data-driven models. Ultimately, we show that this way of working can bring together researchers to generate insights on the impacts of climate change, land use change, and urbanisation on the functioning of the ecosystem, providing scientific support for management and policy decisions.

Keywords

data-model integration, digital twin, FAIR data, multi-scale research, virtual lab, virtual research environment

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.